

The Drift Handling Framework for Open Radio Access Networks: An Experimental Evaluation

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Abstract

The Open Radio Access Network (i.e., Open RAN) aims to transform the inflexible, proprietary RAN into one that is flexible, programmable, and disaggregated to provide intelligent solutions at the network edge for delivering the highly dynamic service demands of Beyond 5G (B5G) networks. Open RAN Working Group-2 (WG2) focuses on the architecture and standards of Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) to meet the Service Level Agreement (SLA) requirements for emerging use cases. The inherent dynamic nature of B5G networks and their applications often leads to AI/ML model performance degradation (i.e., drift), resulting in violations of SLAs, over- or under-provisioning of resources, etc.

This paper proposes a drift handling framework which includes *drift detection*, *analysis*, and its *adaptation* to minimize the SLA violations and efficient resource utilization. The proposed drift handling framework is evaluated across three diverse use cases: (i) Quality of Service prediction, (ii) Channel Quality Indicator prediction, and (iii) User traffic prediction. The experimental evaluations are performed by using the Open RAN Software Community, and OpenAir-Interface FlexRIC platforms with a real-time dataset. Results demonstrate that the proposed drift handling framework outperforms all other considered state-of-the-art frameworks for all the scenarios in terms of the drift detection time, accuracy, precision, F1-score, etc.

Keywords: Open RAN, Beyond 5G network services, RIC control loops, AI/ML, Drift handling.

1. Introduction

In Beyond 5G (B5G), operators strive to deliver a greater number of new services, with increased speed, lower latency, and more connected devices than ever before [1]. To support all these services, the Next Generation Radio Access Network (NG-RAN) enables virtualization and cloud-native frameworks including multi-vendor environments. Several consortia such as operator defined Open and Intelligent Radio Access Networks (O-RAN), Telecom Infra Project (TIP), Open RAN Policy Coalition, and Small Cell Forum are promoting open and disaggregated RAN architectures for B5G networks.

The Open RAN is transforming the current RAN by emphasizing *Openness* and *Intelligence*. *Openness* is introduced by adopting open standard interfaces among the RAN components: the central unit (O-CU), distributed unit (O-DU), and radio unit (O-RU). Whereas, the *Intelligence* is provided by using two different RAN intelligent controllers (RICs) that connect with disaggregated RAN components by using open standard interfaces: Near-real time RIC (Near-RT RIC) and Non-real time RIC (Non-RT RIC). The Near-RT RIC is for the use cases which operate the control loop time between 10 *ms* and 1 *sec*, and the Non-RT RIC is for operations which takes a time scale greater than 1 *sec* [1].

These RICs use Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) to enable intelligence. The O-RAN Working Group 2 (WG2) focuses on the architecture and standards of AI/ML workflows [2]. AI/ML algorithms can handle highly complex network architectures by using the large amount of data collected from different parts of the network through various open standard interfaces. The O-RAN control loops that run at different time scales can be enhanced by leveraging the AI/ML through RICs, however, some challenges must be overcome.

One of the main challenges in B5G networks is maintaining AI/ML model performance consistency. AI/ML model drift is a common issue in B5G networks due to dy-

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dynamic changes in incoming user data traffic, which impacts AI/ML applications [3]. This is especially critical in use cases involving decision-making for network management. Model drift can provide false insights, inaccurate decision-making and potentially leading to severe service interruptions. Moreover, drift can result in inefficient resource allocation and utilization [4] with over/under-provisioning leading to network performance degradation and service disruptions. These issues significantly affect Service Level Agreements (SLAs) between service providers and users. For example, in a smart ambulance use case leveraging B5G, SLAs define a throughput range of 25 Mbps to 400 Mbps, with a response time less than 20 ms. However, model performance degradation can lead to SLA violations [5].

In [6], drift is detected whenever the AI/ML model performance metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, Recall, Precision, etc., surpasses the defined threshold. [7] discussed Drift Detection Method (DDM), Early Drift Detection Method (EDDM), and many other different drift detection solutions based on the online error rate of the AI/ML model. [8] used the *fisher score* to detect the drift — a statistical measure that determines the variation in the considered feature — instead of the online error rate of an AI/ML model. In [9], a Reinforcement Learning (RL) agent triggers drift whenever the similarity (i.e., mean absolute error) between the training and the predicted data exceeds a defined threshold. Another approach in [7], determines drift by observing the changes in the incoming user data through data descriptive statistics such as data range, mean, mode, median, standard deviation, and variance. [10] presents a hybrid approach that monitors both the error rate and changes in the incoming user data. However, adapting to user traffic changes upon drift occurrence is crucial. Various adaptation strategies such as periodic retraining [11], transfer learning [12], and ensemble learning [3] are widely used.

All of the above discussed methods and strategies for drift detection and adaptation share common challenges: they demand substantial data samples for drift detection, require significant computational resources, and are susceptible to false positives. These false positives can lead to resource over-utilization issues and violations of SLAs. Additionally, existing adaptation strategies often lack an analysis of the nature of the detected drift, making it challenging to choose an appropriate adaptation strategy.

To address the consequences of the drift, Open RAN requires robust drift handling frameworks capable of promptly detecting drift occurrences with fewer data samples. Moreover, Open RAN needs an adaptation strategy based on the analysis of the drift that has occurred to adapt the user traffic changes.

This paper focuses on the drift handling framework in Open RAN for maintaining SLAs and efficient resource utilization. This paper proposes the following contributions:

- A novel drift detection algorithm for Open RAN networks.
- A drift handling framework to (i) analyze the drift; (ii) understand the type of drift that has occurred; and (iii) select an adequate drift adaptation strategy.
- Evaluates the proposed drift handling framework for three use cases with an experimental setup: (i) Quality of Service (QoS) prediction; (ii) Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) prediction; and (iii) User traffic prediction. Results show the proposed drift detection algorithm outperforms the state-of-the-art frameworks.
- Investigates the influence of different timing delays in AI/ML life cycle management on control loop response time during the drift adaptation.

2. O-RAN and Drift Understanding

This section provides an overview of the O-RAN architecture and the necessary background needed to understand the drift.

2.1. O-RAN Overview

The O-RAN Alliance was formed in 2018 by combining both the Cloud-RAN and the xRAN efforts to standardize a set of open interfaces in Open RAN architecture [13]. It works with two core principles: (i) *Openness* and (ii) *Intelligence*.

The O-RAN Alliance’s effort complements the 3GPP disaggregated RAN architecture for New Radio (NR) to enable openness in NG-RAN. Here, the next-generation Node B (gNB) is split into three distinct components: O-CU, O-DU, and O-RU. This logical separation among the RAN components allows for the deployment of various functions in different sections of the network with different hardware platforms. The O-RAN Alliance studied several split possibilities suggested by 3GPP between O-RU and O-DU and determined that a 7.2x split is most suited due to the balance between the O-RU and O-DU by supporting flexible data rates and latency [14].

Figure 1 shows the O-RAN architecture, where RAN intelligence is employed through Near-RT and Non-RT RIC. Both the RICs work together to provide a centralized abstraction of the network, which gives operators the ability to implement and deploy their own network functions such as load balancing, QoS management, etc. The Non-RT RIC is part of the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) and also responsible for AI/ML model offline training, policy guidance, enrichment information, and AI/ML model management at the Near-RT RIC. Whereas, the Near-RT RIC interacts with the RAN components and implements the policies received from Non-RT RIC to optimize the RAN components through fine-grained data gathering and corresponding E2 control messages. The AI/ML

models that run at Non- and Near- RT RICs are referred to as rApps and xApps, respectively [14].

The O-RAN introduced open interfaces such as O1, E2, and A1 to connect RICs. The O1 interface collects measurements from the RAN components and sends them to the SMO/Non-RT RIC. Furthermore, the O1 interface enables various management functions such as performance assurance, KPI reporting, customizing network components, and controlling the O-RAN component life cycle. The E2 interface connects between O-CU/O-DU and Near-RT RIC that controls RAN components through E2 control messages. Along with E2 and O1, A1 connects both Near-RT and Non-RT RIC to offer services like policy-based guidance from Non-RT RIC to Near-RT RIC and xApp management. All the data gathered through open interfaces is stored in a data lake and then further processed to train an AI/ML model inside the Non-RT RIC. After validating the trained AI/ML model, the AI/ML model management module in the Non-RT RIC deploys it at the AI/ML inference located in Near-RT RIC/O-DU as an xApp/dApp for RAN optimization [1].

RICs optimize the RAN through Non-RT, Near-RT, and O-DU control loops by leveraging the data collected through the aforementioned interfaces and AI/ML based analytics. The control loop times are based on the requirements of what they control (e.g., MAC scheduling, RAN slicing, load balancing, etc.). The Non-RT RIC executes operations with a time granularity greater than 1 *sec* such as training AI/ML models, policy enforcement, and slice management. The Near-RT RIC handles processes with timescales ranging from 10 *ms* to 1 *sec* (e.g., hosting third-party apps (xApps), load balancing, and handover management). Besides these two, O-DU control loop response time ≤ 10 *ms* to execute operations like Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) prediction, resource scheduling, beamforming, modulation, interference, and blockage detection. The use of AI/ML models through RICs improves the performance of RAN, however, handling the drift that causes due to highly dynamic service demands is critical in Open RAN.

2.2. Drift

The performance of AI/ML models always depends on adopted training or observed datasets. Whenever the model receives unseen data than the observed data, may result in model drift [7]. The drift occurrences can be classified into four types based on changes in the incoming user data distribution [3] as shown in Figure 2:

(a) *Sudden / Abrupt drift*: It happens whenever the input user data changes within a short period. An example of this type of drift in a networking scenario would be, autonomous vehicular traffic patterns before and after the COVID-19 lockdown announcement [15, 16]. Sudden drift can severely impact and disrupt deployed ML models as they are unseen and quick to impact the network.

(b) *Gradual drift*: An extension of the sudden drift where data changes over a long period and AI/ML model

performance degradation occurs gradually. A gradual drift scenario in the networking domain would be sensor monitoring in which the sensor ages and ceases to provide reliable information over time. The gradual drifts are more difficult to detect as their impact on the system happens quietly over a long period.

(c) *Reoccurring drift*: It can be observed whenever the user data follows a recurring pattern over time. In *gradual drift*, the changes in the old data (i.e., observed data) begin to be slowly replaced by the new data. Whereas, in reoccurring drift the old distributions eventually reappear once a certain amount of time has passed.

(d) *Incremental drift*: Incremental drift occurs when data changes (i.e., new data distribution) slowly and continuously. During the transition between observed and new data, it develops intermediate data distributions, that are characterized by both the observed and new data distributions but do not belong to either one as shown in Figure 2. The main difference between *gradual* and *incremental* drift is the intermediate distributions during the transition period [7].

2.2.1. Drift Detection

Drift detection aims to determine the model performance degradation or changes in the incoming user traffic data. There are several drift detection algorithms [7] such as Drift Detection Method (DDM), Early Drift Detection Method (EDDM), ADaptive WINdowing (ADWIN), and One-Class Drift Detector (OCDD).

The fundamental algorithm for drift detection is DDM, which relies on the Probably Approximately Correct (PAC) learning model. PAC assumes that as long as incoming data samples belong to the observed data, AI/ML model prediction error decreases. When DDM detects an error rate increase beyond the defined threshold, it triggers drift. However, DDM has limitations like false alarms, poor performance for *gradual* drift, and requires a significant amount of data. An extension, EDDM [7] considers the distance between prediction errors instead of error rates, being effective for both *gradual* and *sudden* drift. However, EDDM is computationally expensive and prone to false alarms.

ADWIN [7] employs an adaptive sliding window, effectively detecting gradual drifts but relying on mean values, which may not be optimal for characterizing changes in incoming user traffic. OCDD [7] detects drift using a classifier initially trained on specific data and classifies new data instances as outliers by triggering drift when the outlier percentage exceeds a threshold. Retraining the classifier upon drift detection may result in knowledge loss and false alarms. OCDD's limitation includes the need for prior understanding to select parameters like window size (w) and outlier percentage ($p_{outlier}$). Addressing these issues is crucial in the context of Open RAN for effective drift handling.

Figure 1: O-RAN architecture with components and interfaces.

Figure 2: Types of drift based on data distributions.

2.2.2. Drift Analysis

Drift analysis is used to determine the type of drift, which indeed helps in selecting the adequate adaptation

strategy [17]. Drift can be analyzed either by quantifying or by determining the type of drift. In [18], quantified the drift based on the dissimilarity between the observed and new data, which might be useful in selecting a model retraining strategy.

2.2.3. Drift Adaptation

Drift adaptation strategies to deal with the drift that has occurred are important for preserving AI/ML performance consistency. Some of the drift adaptation strategies are as follows:

(i) *Forgetting mechanism* [19]: Whenever the drift occurs, this method forgets the observed data and retrains the model with the newly arrived data. However, forgetting the old data may cause an issue if they appear again in the near future.

(ii) *Blind update or Implicit method* [11]: It periodically retrains the model without the knowledge of drift occurrence. The main disadvantage of this method is a waste of available resources and too much retraining may lead to model over-fitting as well.

(iii) *Informed update* [20, 10]: Enables a statistical method to estimate the changes in the incoming user data and updates the model if changes are introduced. The

AI/ML model update takes place either partially (includes part of the observed data) or completely (ignores observed data) whenever drift is detected. It is important to choose suitable statistical measures for drift detection, otherwise results in triggering false alarms.

3. Related Work

Traditionally, drift has been detected by monitoring the AI/ML model performance [21]. In [22], presents an optimized adaptive sliding window (OASW) method that uses the accuracy of the light gradient boosting machine (LightGBM) model over each sliding window of the incoming IoT data traffic and triggers the drift whenever the model accuracy exceeds the defined threshold and re-trains the model for drift adaptation. The work in [23], integrated the drift handling framework that includes drift detection and adaptation inside the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), which is part of the 5G core network. This framework determines the drift whenever the mean and standard deviation over the incoming data exceeds the defined threshold and performs model retraining for drift adaptation.

In [11], discussed various statistical tests and hypothesis test to determine drift and adapt to the user traffic changes using retraining. Statistical tests such as K-means [24] and Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test [25] are used to compare the observed and incoming user data to investigate the drift occurrence, whereas the hypothesis test analyzes the accuracy of the drift occurrence reported by statistical tests. In [26, 27] significance level is employed to investigate the drift occurrence. However, these tests are prone to false drift alarms.

Another work in [3], presents an ensemble-based drift detection and adaptation. It calculates the median of the obtained rolling mean squared errors over the sliding window and triggers drift if it violates the threshold and re-trains the model. Whereas [28], focuses on drift adaptation using an ensemble learning method that combines both the adaptive random forest (ARF) with DDM, and streaming random patches (SRP) with ADWIN in the IoT data streams. An extended work in [29], employed ensemble learning using ARF with both ADWIN and EDDM, k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) with ADWIN for drift adaptation. However, these approaches are limited to handling both sudden and gradual drift only. Also computationally expensive and often requires high execution time due to the aggregation of many models.

In [30], a clustering method was employed to determine changes in the incoming user traffic. The user mobility data is collected from a group of gNBs, and an AI/ML model is trained for each gNB to predict the gNB for each incoming UE. If the incoming UE does not belong to any of the observed gNB clusters, then it is assigned to a cluster called *super outlier*. Whenever the number of UEs data points in *super outlier* surpasses the defined threshold, then triggers the drift and the model is retrained. The

work in [31], leverages federated node model updates to determine drift in federated networked systems. Through the dimensionality reduction, clustering, and modeling of normal federated node update behaviour, the proposed framework can identify the drift based on a distance-based threshold calculation.

In [12, 32, 33], discussed various adaptation strategies using RL. RL agent is used to select the suitable adaptation strategy from the available actions such as retraining (i.e., all the layers of AI/ML model will get updated), fine-tuning (i.e., adjusting the parameters of already trained model), freezing (i.e., prevents desired layers from being modified), and discarding some layers of an AI/ML model based on the maximum reward obtained. However, RL agent actions are limited to the only AI/ML model under consideration and the time required for selecting an appropriate adaptation strategy by performing different actions might not be suitable for latency sensitive applications.

To the best of our knowledge, no earlier study presented a drift handling framework for Open RAN and the influence of AI/ML model adaptation on the RAN control loop response time. This paper presents a novel drift handling framework for Open RAN which can detect the drift promptly after its occurrence as well as avoid false alarms, and provide an adequate adaptation strategy based on drift type. In addition, this paper also investigates the impact of drift adaptation as well as resource allocation on RAN control loop response time.

4. Proposed Drift Handling Framework

Figure 3 shows the proposed drift handling framework for Open RAN. By actively monitoring the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the deployed model, our framework is generalizable to all types of drifts.

The proposed framework has the following advantages when compared to other drift handling frameworks:

- The proposed drift handling framework addresses both drift detection and drift adaptation with drift analysis that could help in selecting an appropriate adaptation strategy, unlike many frameworks that focus on either drift detection or drift adaptation.
- In contrast to existing frameworks such as One-Class Drift Detector (OCDD) [34], Model Drift in Dynamic Networks (MDDN) [3], 5G Core Network Drift Adaptation (5GCNDA) [23], and Concept Neurons Drift Handling (CNDH) [35], which are primarily focused on retraining or partial updates of the model as adaptation strategies, our proposed framework encompasses both retraining and the selection of an appropriate model for replacement based on the nature of the drift.
- The proposed framework detects drift and updates the model depending on model performance degradation, which ensures that the model is only updated

Figure 3: Architecture of the proposed drift handling framework.

when necessary which could result in efficient usage of resources.

- The proposed framework analyzes the drift and addresses the drift type that has occurred (sudden or incremental), occurrence time (i.e., when it has started), and its duration (i.e., how long it has occurred).
- The proposed framework effectively adapts to different datasets by automatically optimizing hyperparameters using the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm.

As shown in Figure 3, the framework initialization process begins with data collection from various open standard interfaces such as O1, E2, and A1 from the RAN components (i.e., E2 node) through the xApps (e.g., Key Performance Metric (KPM) xApp). The data collection is common for both Non- and Near- RT RIC, and it also contains many KPMs with different granularities, from which an AI/ML model may take input data for training and inference depending on the prediction task.

The data collected from the E2 node can be used for the training and testing of an AI/ML model. The training and testing phase generates an AI/ML inference which contains the learned weights of the given dataset and it can be deployed across the RAN components according to the requirements. AI/ML model management — located at Non-RT RIC as shown in Figure 1 — deploys AI/ML inference across the RAN via the O1 interface, based on the use case being evaluated to make a prediction, as well as the amount of data the model requires and the latency requirements.

The deployed AI/ML inference model (i.e., rApp or xApp) infers the desired metric for given time steps and provides to the corresponding RAN components through standard open interfaces. The AI/ML inference predicted values to the corresponding actual values can be obtained from the data stream through xApps.

Both the predicted and corresponding actual values are used for the proposed drift detection algorithm. The RMSE [36] as in Equation 1 is calculated for each sliding window and triggers drift when the RMSE exceeds the defined threshold for a determined number of sliding windows continuously.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

where, y_i is real output and \hat{y}_i is the predicted output from respective model. The drift analysis is performed upon drift detection, otherwise the AI/ML Inference continues. The drift adaptation determines whether to retrain the existing model or replace it with a suitable model based on the type of drift that has occurred.

The following section describes the proposed algorithms for drift detection, analysis and adaptation:

4.1. Proposed Algorithms

The implementation of the proposed drift handling framework is based on the drift detection, analysis, and adaptation algorithms.

Algorithm 1 depicts the proposed window-based drift handling framework. This Algorithm internally calls three different algorithms: (i) drift detection in Algorithm 2; (ii) drift analysis in Algorithm 3; and (iii) drift adaptation in Algorithm 4. The parameters definition or variables utilized in the algorithms are reported in Table 1.

Algorithm 1 starts by loading WS , $Accuracy_{th}$, SLA , $ModelList$, p_d , and a_d for a given $LeadTime$, where $LeadTime$ is defined as the period for which forecasts are needed — the future time for which the data need to be predicted. The values for input parameters such as $RMSE_{th}$ and $flag_{vth}$ can be determined using the PSO algorithm. The PSO is a popular bio-inspired algorithm that is used to search for the optimal hyperparameters in the solution space. The PSO initializes a group of random

Table 1: Description of variables used in Algorithms

Acronym	Referring to / Definition
WS	Window size which includes required number of data samples.
$RMSE_{th}$	RMSE threshold
$flag$	Variable to indicate whether the window is exceeding RMSE threshold (i.e., flag 1) or not (i.e., flag 0)
$flag_{list}$	A list contains $flag$ values of each window
$flag_{vth}$	$flag$ violation threshold
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization is an algorithm, useful to determine optimal values for the given input parameters.
f_p	percentage of $flag1$ over all the windows (TW)
W_{limit}	Number of $flag1$ conservatives to consider
$Accuracy_{th}$	AI/ML model threshold accuracy
$drift$	Variable which indicates drift occurrence
$drift_{type}$	Variable which stores type of drift; either Incremental or Sudden
SLA	The service level agreement made between the operators and the users based on applications [5]
$Total_{delay}$	Time including AI/ML model prediction, retraining and other delays as in Equation 5
TW	Total number of windows
$RMSE_{save}$	A list contains RMSE of each window
ModelList	A list contains all the available AI/ML models at Non-RT RIC
p_d	Prediction data list
a_d	Actual data list
p_w	Prediction data window
a_w	Actual data window
$model_{sla}$	A list contains all the AI/ML models that meet SLA after including their prediction time to the total delay (i.e., $Total_{delay}$ as in Equation 5)
$model_{accuracy}$	Accuracy of an AI/ML model
$model_{eligible}$	A list contains all the models which are satisfying both the required latency and accuracy
w	Window size for OCDD
$p_{outlier}$	Outlier percentage threshold for OCDD

solutions (i.e., swarm) for each hyperparameter. Each solution is represented as a particle in a multidimensional search space and all the randomly generated solutions (i.e., particles) are distributed within the search space. Further, each particle determines local and global solutions and then traverses toward the optimal solution in the search space using position and velocity vectors. Updation of both the position and the velocity continues for a defined number of iterations, which produces an optimal solution for the corresponding hyperparameters. The PSO requires several input parameters to function effectively. These parameters include the number of particles, the number of iterations, and the inertia weight, which serves to stabilize particle movement. Moreover, PSO employs the cognitive coefficient to assess a particle’s performance to previously

Algorithm 1 Window based Drift Handling

```

1: Input :  $WS, Accuracy_{th}, flag = \{\}, RMSE_{save} = \{\}, ModelList, SLA, p_d, a_d, drift, drift_{type} = \{Incremental, Sudden\}$ 
2:  $RMSE_{th}, flag_{vth} \leftarrow$  Select using PSO
3: Output : Action according to the drift type
4:  $L \leftarrow size(p_d)$ 
5:  $TW = \frac{L}{WS}$ 
6: while data_available do
7:    $drift \leftarrow drift\_detection(p_d, a_d, WS, TW, RMSE_{th}, flag_{vth})$  (Refer Algorithm 2)
8:   if ( $drift = 1$ ) then
9:      $drift_{type} \leftarrow drift\_analysis(RMSE_{save}, flag, TW)$  (Refer Algorithm 3)
10:    if ( $drift_{type} = Incremental$ ) then
11:       $model\_selection(ModelList, SLA, Accuracy_{th})$  (Refer Algorithm 4)
12:    else
13:      Trigger AI/ML Model Training
14:    end if
15:  end if
16: end while

```

obtained value, and the social coefficient to evaluate performance relative to neighboring particles. Finally, a convergence threshold is employed to determine when optimal values for the hyperparameters have been reached. More details on PSO can be found in [37].

Considering the length of the prediction data, calculates the total number of windows (TW) (see lines 4-5). When data is available, Algorithm 2 is employed, utilizing the average RMSE across all windows to assess drift detection (see line 7). Once the occurrence of drift is confirmed, proceeds to analyze the drift using Algorithm 3, wherein the $flag$ violation is considered to identify the type of drift (see lines 8-9). Finally, the drift adaptation calls Algorithm 4 for incremental drift, otherwise triggers retraining if the drift is sudden (see lines 10-13). In the following, details of the proposed $drift_detection$, $drift_analysis$, and $drift_adaptation$ algorithms are provided.

4.1.1. Drift Detection

Algorithm 2 describes the proposed drift detection, which is based on the average RMSE over a defined WS . The RMSE metric is considered because the AI/ML prediction model errors are likely to follow the normal distribution and it can be a better metric to represent the model’s performance [36]. The proposed method evaluates drift by looking at both the predicted and actual values. This is different from other drift techniques such as DDM, EDDM, ADWIN, and OCDD as described in Sec. 2.2.1, which only look at either actual or prediction value. Here, the only way for drift adaptation was to retrain the currently running AI/ML model, independent of what kind of drift had happened. As the AI/ML model predicts the near future for a given $LeadTime$, both actual and pre-

Algorithm 2 Drift Detection Algorithm

```
1: Initialize:  $l = 1$ 
2:  $drift\_detection(p_d, a_d, WS, TW, RMSE_{th}, flag_{vth})$ 
3: while ( $l \leq TW$ ) do
4:    $p_w = p_d[WS * (l - 1) \text{ to } WS * (l) - 1]$ 
5:    $a_w = a_d[WS * (l - 1) \text{ to } WS * (l) - 1]$ 
6:   calculate  $RMSE_w(p_w, a_w)$ 
7:    $RMSE_{save.append} \leftarrow RMSE_w$ 
8:   if  $RMSE_w > RMSE_{th}$  then
9:      $flag.append \leftarrow 1$ 
10:     $flag_{list} \leftarrow flag$ 
11:     $count \leftarrow count + 1$ 
12:   else
13:      $flag.append \leftarrow 0$ 
14:      $flag_{list} \leftarrow flag$ 
15:   end if
16:    $l \leftarrow l + 1$ 
17: end while
18:  $f_p = \frac{count}{TW}$ 
19: if  $f_p > flag_{vth}$  then
20:    $return \leftarrow 1$ 
21: else
22:    $return \leftarrow 0$ 
23: end if
```

dicted values are collected and split based on the given WS to compute the RMSE of each window (i.e., $RMSE_w$) (see lines 4-7). The RMSE of each window is compared with the $RMSE_{th}$, and a flag 1 is assigned if it surpasses the $RMSE_{th}$; otherwise, a flag 0 is assigned (see lines 8-16). Drift is determined whenever the percentage of flag 1s in $flag_{list}$ exceeds the $flag_{vth}$, indicating that drift has occurred (see lines 18-22).

4.1.2. Drift Analysis

The proposed drift analysis algorithm examines the flag 1 pattern to determine drift type. Consecutive threshold violations can provide information about user traffic changes and can be useful in identifying drift types [38]. Algorithm 3 determines the number of consecutive threshold violations to check over all the windows as a function of both the SLA and the $LeadTime$. This function is derived after observing the convergence of the model's accuracy for various datasets with different values of $LeadTime$. Note that the derived function is working well for the datasets under consideration [39].

The drift type is identified based on the RMSE of each window and corresponding flag pattern. *Incremental drift* is discovered when the RMSE values for the corresponding flag pattern are in ascending order; otherwise *sudden drift* is obtained. Note that only two types of drift analysis are considered in this paper, and understanding other drift type(s) is yet to be investigated.

Algorithm 3 takes the $RMSE_{save}$, $flag_{list}$, and TW as inputs and return the drift type as output. Initially, Algorithm 3 calculates the fraction of SLA in $LeadTime$

Algorithm 3 Drift Analysis Algorithm

```
1:  $drift\_analysis(RMSE_{save}, flag, TW)$ 
2:  $len = \frac{LeadTime}{SLA}$ 
3:  $W_{limit} = \lfloor \frac{len}{WS} \rfloor$ 
4: for ( $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $TW$ ) do
5:   if ( $flag_{list}[i] = 1$ ) then
6:      $count \leftarrow count + 1$ 
7:      $RMSE_{temp} \leftarrow RMSE_{save}[i]$ 
8:   else
9:      $count \leftarrow 0$ 
10:  end if
11:  if ( $count = W_{limit}$ ) then
12:    if ( $RMSE_{temp}$  is in increasing order) then
13:       $return \leftarrow Incremental$ 
14:      break
15:    else
16:       $return \leftarrow Sudden$ 
17:      break
18:    end if
19:     $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
20:  end if
21: end for
```

and further divides with WS to determine the number of consecutive flag 1 values to check (see lines 2-3). Analyzing the flag 1 patterns could help in understanding drift type (see lines 4-9). Whenever the flag pattern is found and corresponding RMSE values are in increasing order then it is considered as an *incremental drift* otherwise a *sudden drift* (see lines 11-19).

4.1.3. Drift Adaptation

To adapt to the drift that has occurred, the proposed framework offers adaptation strategies such as retraining the model or switching to another suitable model based on the drift type as shown in Figure 4. Retraining is advised for *sudden drift* because only a single data distribution replaces the old one. Thus, retraining could help in learning the patterns of new data distribution. In *incremental drift*, several mixed distributions are present during the transition as shown in Figure 2. Hence, a retraining strategy is not a viable option; rather switching to a suitable model that has been periodically updated is preferred.

To select a suitable model for *incremental drift*, the proposed framework considers a dynamic model selection for replacement in Algorithm 4. Initially, among all the available models, Algorithm 4 selects the models that meet both the SLA and the $Accuracy_{th}$. The model whichever has the best accuracy among all the models can be used to replace the existing model.

In Non-RT RIC a group of traditional and AI/ML time series models [40] such as Triple Exponential Smoothing (TES), Double Exponential Smoothing (DES), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Transformer (TS) are available and represented with $ModelList$. For each model in $ModelList$, Algorithm 4 exploits $Total_{delay}$ obtained in

Figure 4: Drift adaptation under various drift scenarios.

Algorithm 4 Dynamic Model Selection for Replacement

```

1:  $model\_selection(ModelList, SLA, Accuracy_{th})$ 
2: for  $model \in ModelList$  do
3:   if  $Total_{delay} \leq SLA$  then
4:      $model_{sla}.append \leftarrow model$ 
5:   end if
6:   if  $model_{accuracy} \geq Accuracy_{th}$  then
7:      $model_{eligible}.append \leftarrow model_{sla}$ 
8:   end if
9: end for
10: sort  $model_{eligible}$  based on accuracy
11: return  $(model_{eligible})_{index=1}$ 

```

Equation 5 to check whether it is satisfying desired SLA or not (see lines 2-5). All the models that meet the desired SLA are stored in a list (i.e., $model_{sla}$) and then checks the accuracy of each model in the list (see lines 6-8). Models that meet the threshold accuracy are sorted in order of their accuracy and available in Non-RT RIC list $model_{eligible}$. When incremental drift occurs, the existing model will be replaced with the best performing model from $model_{eligible}$ list (see lines 10-11).

5. Experimental setup

The proposed drift handling framework is evaluated in three different use cases: (i) *Quality of Service (QoS) prediction* over the O-RAN software community (OSC) platform, (ii) *Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) prediction* over the OpenAirInterface (OAI) FlexRIC platform, and (iii) *User traffic prediction* using a real-time dataset. Description of each use case and corresponding experimental setup as follows:

5.1. QoS prediction

The service quality that network providers offer to their subscribers (i.e., users) is measured by QoS. However, inaccurate QoS prediction can result in either over- or under-provisioning of resources, with the latter causing severe SLA violations and longer delays due to the allocation of a small number of physical resource blocks (PRBs), while the former results in resource waste due to the allocation of a larger number of PRBs than required [41].

To deal with these challenges, the proposed drift handling framework is integrated with OSC RIC to evaluate the drift scenario for the QoS use case as shown in Figure 5. The OSC focuses on implementing Open RAN solutions that adhere to the O-RAN Alliance’s designs and requirements. Figure 5 shows the considered experimental setup for evaluating the QoS use case. This setup mainly includes the proposed drift handling framework application programming interface (API) (located at Non-RT RIC) integrated with Near-RT RIC framework and an E2 simulator.

The OSC Near-RT RIC framework (F-release), an E2 simulator, and various open interfaces are deployed. Here, the Near-RT RIC framework is deployed as a Kubernetes pod — a collection of containers running inside a node of a Kubernetes cluster. The OSC Near-RT RIC includes an E2 manager, a routing manager, a subscription manager, an app manager, and a shared database (i.e., InfluxDB). These components are deployed as microservices within the Kubernetes cluster. When a xApp is onboarded into the Near-RT RIC, it writes statistics into the common database (i.e., InfluxDB). Open interfaces such as A1, E2, and O1 are also utilized as shown in Figure 5.

Within the Near-RT RIC, a key performance metric monitoring (KPMON) xApp is responsible for monitoring and reporting the statistics of each layer in the RAN to an InfluxDB database. It periodically writes the statistics of the data units used for each layer, and an API function inside the database measures the cell throughput each time the data is updated. Moreover, the QoS Prediction (QP) xApp is also onboarded in the Near-RT RIC. The QP xApp predicts the QoS values and writes into the InfluxDB database, and it utilizes a three-layer Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) model [40, 16] with 100 hidden units in each layer, along with a rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function. The status of the QP xApp onboarded into the Near-RT RIC is shown in Figure 6.

An OSC E2 simulator consists of 5G core, O-CU, O-DU, and O-RU. These components establish communication with the Near-RT RIC through the E2 control messages such as (1) E2 setup request; (2) E2 setup subscription; and (3) E2 setup indication as shown in Figure 5. Additionally, the E2 simulator can be connected by multiple UEs with varying data rates configured through a customized JavaScript Object Notation (*json*) file.

Figure 5: Experimental setup for evaluating the QoS use case with proposed drift handling framework.

Note that the current F-release of OSC does not include a complete implementation of the SMO and the Non-RT RIC frameworks [42]. Therefore, to evaluate the QoS prediction use case using the proposed framework, the missing functionalities in the OSC platform are implemented and deployed on a bare metal server, for example, performing the off-line AI/ML models training and onboard them in the Near-RT RIC as a microservice using the *dms_cli* tool. Additionally, the proposed framework is implemented as a Representational State Transfer API (REST API). It monitors changes in user traffic by accessing real-time data (i.e., throughput) from the InfluxDB database through a customized API.

The Near-RT RIC and E2 simulator are connected and integrated with the proposed drift handling framework deployed in Non-RT RIC to provide AI/ML model management functionalities such as data collection and preparation, AI/ML model training, and its deployment.

```

root@ric:/home/ric/appmgr/xapp_orchestrator/dev/xapp_onboarder# kubectl get pods -n ricxapp
NAME                                READY   STATUS    RESTARTS   AGE
ricxapp-hwxapp-684d8d675b-bsbgg     1/1    Running   0           36h
ricxapp-qp-5f6fc7b746-c4rbf        1/1    Running   0           22h

```

Figure 6: Status of on-boarding the QP xApp into the Near-RT RIC.

5.2. CQI prediction

In general, UE provides channel state information (CSI) to the gNB, with CQI being a key parameter. CQI is a 4-bit value that represents the current quality of the channel. Based on the CQI value, the scheduler at MAC allocates resource blocks and assigns a modulation and coding scheme (MCS) to determine the data rate that could be transmitted over a channel. Inaccurate CQI can cause over- or under-provisioning of resources and improper MCS degrades the UE performance. The highly dynamic service demands of B5G networks can produce changes in user data, resulting in drift and inaccurate CQI

values [43]. The proposed drift handling mechanism is integrated with CQI use case as shown in Figure 7 for drift detection, analysis and adaptation mechanism.

Figure 7 shows the considered experimental setup for evaluating the CQI use case. This setup mainly consists of a proposed drift handling framework API, a Near-RT RIC (i.e., OAI FlexRIC), and an E2 Node — namely the gNB.

The OAI FlexRIC framework that provides Near-RT RIC functionalities, an E2 node, 5G core, and various interfaces are deployed. The OAI FlexRIC framework is integrated with the E2 node and contains components such as (i) FlexRIC agent — helps to integrate into a base station (i.e., E2 node); (ii) FlexRIC controller — creates specific controllers through the service models (SMs); and (iii) E2 protocol abstraction (E2AP) — creates a communication interface between different transport protocols. In addition, the OAI FlexRIC framework also has open interfaces like E2, E2AP, a message handler and a generic RAN function API. Integrated a CQI prediction model along with the OAI FlexRIC to predict the real time CQI values over time and store in the database. The predicted CQI values can be provided to the MAC scheduler through E2 control messages to allocate resources efficiently.

An OAI gNB (i.e., E2 node) is deployed with the support of E2 control messages and leverages the OAI 5G core to serve the user data requests. . Additionally, an OAI nrUE is used to connect the 5G core through gNB and also multiple UEs can be configured. Note that the current OAI FlexRIC release does not have an implementation of the SMO and the Non-RT RIC frameworks. Thus, the Non-RT RIC functionalities are implemented to evaluate the CQI prediction use case using the proposed drift handling framework. Moreover, the proposed framework is developed as a REST API, which extracts real-time CQI values and predicted CQI values from the database to evaluate the drift detection, analysis, and an appropriate adap-

Figure 7: Experimental setup for evaluating the CQI use case with proposed drift handling framework.

tation strategy.

The emulated UE is connected to the 5G core through the gNB with Near-RT RIC module and integrated with the proposed framework.

5.3. User traffic prediction

The ever-increasing user traffic and highly dynamic service demands in B5G networks are likely to impact user traffic and bandwidth demands [44]. Mobile network operators (MNOs) are required to deal with such complex architecture to guarantee user demands. Predicting network conditions with AI/ML enables user-centric strategies for MNOs, aiding network service management and flexible policy configurations.

A real-time dataset is considered and obtained from the Colosseum testbed [45]. The dataset contains three slices: enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Machine-type Communications (MTC), and Ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC), with UEs distributed randomly across the slices both in static and moving conditions. The eMBB slice user traffic in *static conditions* is considered and trained an AI/ML model to predict the near future user traffic for a given *LeadTime*. To evaluate the drift scenario, the eMBB slice user traffic in *moving conditions* is introduced and the proposed drift handling framework is able to successfully identify the driftAPI accesses both predicted and corresponding actual values to evaluate the drift scenario. The similar experiments for each slice, as well as a mix of them, are considered to assess the performance of the proposed framework across multiple instances.

The following section discusses the results obtained for all three use cases, comparing the outcomes of the proposed framework with those of other considered frameworks.

6. Results

This section presents the considered performance metrics and performance comparison between the proposed drift handling framework and other frameworks such as: One-Class Drift Detector (OCDD) [34], Model Drift in Dynamic Networks (MDDN) [3], 5G Core Network Drift Adaptation (5GCNDA) [23], and Concept Neurons Drift Handling (CNDH) [35]. Also, evaluated these for the considered three use cases: (i) *QoS prediction*; (ii) *CQI prediction*; and the (iii) *User traffic prediction* for performance comparison. Finally, an analysis of the impact of drift adaptation and resource allocation on the RAN control loop response time is discussed.

6.1. Performance Metrics

The following Key metrics are considered to evaluate the performance of the proposed drift framework:

(i) *Drift detection time* is defined as the time taken to identify model performance degradation or changes in the incoming user traffic. A longer detection time indicates a lower performance as it delays to determine model drift.

(ii) *True Positive (TP) Ratio* is defined as the ratio between correctly detected drifts and the total number of drift occurrences. This is also referred as *sensitivity* or *recall*. A high TP ratio indicates that the corresponding

framework is effective at detecting drift when it occurs, minimizing the false drift alarms [12].

$$TP \text{ Ratio} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

(iii) *False Negative (FN) Ratio* is defined as the ratio between the falsely detected drifts and the total number of drift occurrences. A high FN ratio implies that the framework is not sensitive enough to detect drift occurrences [12].

$$FN \text{ Ratio} = \frac{FN}{TP + FN}$$

(iv) *False Positive (FP) Ratio* is defined as the proportion of instances where the framework falsely triggers a drift event when it did not occur. A high FP ratio indicates that the framework triggers false alarms frequently, potentially leading to unnecessary model updates [12].

$$FP \text{ Ratio} = \frac{FP}{TP + FN}$$

(v) *Accuracy* is defined as the overall correctness of a framework. A high accuracy indicates that the framework detects the drift promptly after its occurrence.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP}{TP + FN + FP}$$

(vi) *Precision* is defined as the accuracy of the correct decisions made by a framework regarding the drift occurrence. A high precision value means that when the framework triggers the drift, it is often correct.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

(vii) *F1-score* is defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It balances the trade-off between recall and precision, and a high score indicates a better balance between them.

$$F1 - score = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

6.2. Performance Comparison

The proposed drift handling framework is compared with other frameworks to evaluate its performance. The functionality of the other frameworks that are considered for comparison with the proposed framework is as follows:

- *OCDD [34]*: Observes the incoming user traffic by employing a supervised classifier (i.e., SVM) and detects the drift whenever the outlier percentage exceeds the defined threshold. To adapt to the user traffic changes, it triggers the model retraining. This framework uses parameters such as window size (i.e., w) and an outlier percentage threshold (i.e., θ). Also, these values are user defined based on the use case under consideration.

- *MDDN [3]*: The framework measures statistics such as median and median absolute deviation (MAD) as shown in Equation 2, during the test phase and determines the threshold values that can capture the observed data. It triggers the drift, whenever the MAD score exceeds the obtained threshold and re-trains the model to predict further.

$$MAD = median(|y_i - \hat{y}|) \quad (2)$$

where y_i is the incoming data sample and \hat{y} is the median of the data samples in a considered window. The median can be determined during the training.

- *5GCNDA [23]*: In this framework, both the mean (i.e., μ) and standard deviation (i.e., σ) are measured during the training. It triggers drift, whenever the μ and σ measured over a window exceeds Equation 3 and re-trains the model.

$$\mu + n \times \sigma \quad (3)$$

where μ is the calculated mean, σ is the calculated standard deviation, and n is a positive integer used to control the conservativeness of the threshold. These values can be determined during data pre-processing.

- *CNDH [35]*: Measures the mean absolute error (MAE) as shown in Equation 4 over the considered window and triggers drift whenever it surpasses the defined threshold and re-trains the model.

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{WS} |x_i - y_i|}{WS} \quad (4)$$

where, x_i , y_i , and WS are observed data, predicted data, and the window size, respectively. This value can be determined during the model training.

Here, Window Size (WS) for MDDN, 5GCNDA, CNDH, and the proposed framework is considered the same, whereas for the OCDD w and θ , are chosen according to suggestions provided in [34] based on the dataset.

To assess the performance of the proposed drift handling framework with other frameworks, user traffic data that have different traffic patterns using the Distributed Internet Traffic Generator (D-ITG) [46] tool is generated. D-ITG is a powerful tool for generating various types of network traffic including Constant, Uniform, Exponential, Pareto, Cauchy, Normal, Poisson and Gamma, and many other. Five different user traffic patterns are generated — Normal, Uniform, Exponential, Poisson, and Gamma distribution user traffic patterns — in which each user traffic pattern is comprised of 10,000 user traffic data samples for each ms as shown in Figure 8. The input parameters of each considered framework are detailed in Table 2 and

Figure 8: Performance evaluation of drift handling frameworks for drift detection

Table 2: Input Parameters of considered Drift Handling Frameworks

Framework	Parameter	Value
OCDD	w	200
	$p_{outlier}$	0.4
MDDN	MAD	23
5GCNDA	μ	5
	σ	11
	n	2
CNDH	MAE	15
Proposed	WS	40
	$RMSE_{th}$	18
	$flag_{vth}$	0.3

employed PSO to obtain both $RMSE_{th}$ and $flag_{vth}$) for the proposed framework.

Figure 8 illustrates the performance of the proposed framework in comparison to others for drift detection. Initially, the evaluation starts with normal distribution from 0 to 10000 ms. The new user traffic patterns — namely User Traffic Pattern 1 (UTP1) follows Uniform distribution, User Traffic Pattern 2 (UTP2) follows Exponential distribution, User Traffic Pattern 3 (UTP3) follows Poisson distribution and User Traffic Pattern 4 (UTP4) follows gamma distribution — are introduced at time intervals of 10000 ms, 20000 ms, 30000 ms, and 40000 ms and highlighted in *Actual* legend of Figure. For each of these traffic patterns, various drift detection frameworks such as OCDD, MDDN, 5GCNDA, CNDH and the proposed are employed to detect the drift.

All these frameworks identified the drift at specific time intervals with the corresponding UTPs as follows:

- *UTP1*: the OCDD, MDDN, 5GCNDA, CNDH and the proposed frameworks are detected the traffic change at 10400 *ms*, 10310 *ms*, 10215 *ms*, 10180 *ms*, and 10120 *ms*, respectively.
- *UTP2*: the OCDD, MDDN, 5GCNDA, CNDH and the proposed frameworks are detected the traffic change at 20480 *ms*, 20260 *ms*, 20290 *ms*, 20190 *ms* and 20145 *ms*, respectively.
- *UTP3*: the OCDD, MDDN, 5GCNDA, CNDH and the proposed frameworks are detected the traffic change at 30350 *ms*, 30300 *ms*, 30310 *ms*, 30210 *ms*, and 30130 *ms*, respectively.
- *UTP4*: the OCDD, MDDN, 5GCNDA, CNDH and the proposed frameworks are detected the traffic change at 40220 *ms*, 40270 *ms*, 40195 *ms*, 40125 *ms*, and 40110 *ms*, respectively.

From the above all the considered different user distribution traffic patterns, the proposed framework can detect traffic changes early among all other considered frameworks.

Figure 9 displays the time taken by each framework to detect drift, as inferred from Figure 8. From Figure 9, it is observed that the proposed framework promptly triggers drift detection after its occurrence. Early drift detection is crucial for quick model retraining and replacement. The proposed framework outperforms in detecting drift occurrence compared to other frameworks.

Figure 9: Performance evaluation of the frameworks for drift detection (in *ms*)

Figure 8 reveals that both MDDN and 5GCNDA frameworks are performing closer to the CNDH. Therefore, for the sake of a more concise and representative

comparison, three frameworks are considered — Proposed, CNDH, and OCDD. Figure 10 depicts the True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN) ratios of the proposed, CNDH, and OCDD frameworks. Here, the proposed, CNDH, and OCDD frameworks have comparable TP ratios of 0.97%, 0.91%, and 0.82%, respectively. However, the ideal framework should not have many FPs or false alarms, since false alarms can result in resource utilization issues and SLA violations. Moreover, the ideal framework should not have a high FN ratio, so that it may not miss any drift occurrences [12]. The proposed framework performs better due to lower FP and FN ratios when compared to CNDH and OCDD ratios.

Figure 10: TP, FP, and FN ratios of three drift detection frameworks.

Other performance metrics such as Accuracy, Precision and F1-score are listed in Table 3 for all the considered frameworks. The proposed drift handling framework obtains an accuracy, precision, and f1-score as 0.95%, 0.98%, and 0.97% respectively, and outperforms the remaining frameworks.

Table 3: Drift detection performance comparison of each framework

Framework	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	F1-score (%)
OCDD	0.72	0.86	0.84
MDDN	0.81	0.89	0.91
5GCNDA	0.81	0.93	0.89
CNDH	0.82	0.90	0.90
Proposed	0.95	0.98	0.97

Moreover, the proposed framework is evaluated with others as a function of three different use cases as follows:

6.3. Quality of Service (QoS) Prediction

The parameters used for each of the considered frameworks to evaluate the QoS use case are as follows:

- *Proposed*: The considered parameters, the WS , $RMSE_{th}$, and $flag_{vth}$ are set to 15, 15, 0.31, respectively.
- *CNDH*: The MAE parameter is set to 30.
- *OCDD*: The parameter values for both w and p_w are set to 80 and 0.4.

The deployed QP xApp is built using the LSTM model, which is trained with data collected from KPMON xApp

Figure 11: Evaluation of QoS prediction xApp with the proposed drift handling framework.

and other datasets [45, 39]. In this use case, the user traffic changes are introduced at 140 *ms* as shown in Figure 11. The proposed drift handling framework detects the drift over the time interval [140 – 200] *ms* and the nature of the drift is determined as *Sudden*, after analyzing it. Our proposed framework triggers model retraining (i.e. updating the current QP xApp) as an adaptation strategy and replaces the model around 290 *ms*. In contrast, other frameworks such as CNDH and OCDD trigger drift at different times, specifically 210 *ms* and 315 *ms*, respectively. These frameworks then replace the updated models for drift adaptation at later time points, precisely 330 *ms* and 443 *ms*, respectively.

Furthermore, to evaluate the performance of the considered frameworks, traffic rate over a duration of 3600 *seconds* is considered. Figure 12 represents a sampled Probability Mass Function (PMF) that illustrates the relation between the time required to detect drift and the frequency of drift occurrences. On the Y-axis of Figure 12, occurrences represent the percentage of instances in which each framework takes a specific time to trigger the drift, whereas the X-axis is the time taken to determine the change in user traffic. The OCDD framework exhibits a maximum of 26% occurrences at 110 *ms*, whereas the CNDH shows approximately 28% occurrences at 80 *ms*. In contrast, the proposed framework achieves approximately 33% occurrences at 70 *ms*, respectively. The proposed framework effectively determines the drift compared to the other frameworks.

6.4. Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) Prediction

An LSTM model is built using the CQI data samples collected from KPI Monitoring xApp as well as other data

Figure 12: Sampled PMF of drift detection for QoS use case

sets [45]. The parameters used for each of the considered frameworks to evaluate the CQI use case are as follows:

- *Proposed*: The considered parameters, the WS , $RMSE_{th}$, and $flag_{vth}$ are set to 20, 15, 0.31, respectively.
- *CNDH*: The MAE parameter is set to 30.
- *OCDD*: The parameter values for both w and p_w are set to 80 and 0.4.

A group of AI/ML models such as TES, DES, and Transformer are considered in *ModelList* in to select a suitable model to replace. Several UEs are launched randomly and kept running for a long period, which caused drift as a result of UE interference and its impact can be observed from 90 *ms* onwards in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Proposed drift handling framework evaluation for CQI use case.

Figure 13 depicts the performance of the proposed framework along with others for CQI prediction use case. The proposed drift handling framework detected the drift over the time interval $[90 - 170]$ ms and after analyzing it, identified as *Incremental*, for which the Algorithm 4 selects a model to replace the current model. The *Transformer* model is selected among all the available models and replaced it with the current model at 300 ms. In contrast, other frameworks including CNDH and OCDD detected drift at varying time points: 195 ms and 280 ms, respectively. These frameworks initiated model replacement upon detecting drift, occurring at 320 ms and 410 ms. Notably, the proposed adaptation strategy showcased a distinct advantage by selecting the *Transformer* model for replacement, which outperformed the retrained models employed by the other frameworks in accurately predicting the CQI during incremental drift scenarios.

Figure 14 represents a sampled PMF that illustrates the relation between the time required to detect changes in the user traffic and the frequency of user traffic changes. Here, the user arrivals spanning a 3600 seconds duration are considered for assessing the performance of the frameworks. The OCDD framework exhibits a maximum of 21% occurrences at 140 ms, whereas the CNDH shows approximately 18% occurrences at 120 ms. In contrast, the proposed framework achieves approximately 24% and 20% occurrences at 90 ms and 100 ms, respectively. The proposed framework effectively determines the drift compared to the other frameworks.

Figure 14: Sampled PMF of drift detection for CQI use case

6.5. User Traffic Prediction

The parameters used for each of the considered frameworks to evaluate the user traffic prediction use case are as follows:

- *Proposed*: The considered parameters, the WS , $RMSE_{th}$, and $flag_{vth}$ are set to 10, 8.5, 0.29, respectively.
- *CNDH*: The MAE parameter is set to 12.
- *OCDD*: The parameter values for both w and p_w are set to 60 and 0.27.

Figure 15: Evaluation of sudden drift scenario over a real-time user traffic dataset.

The drift scenario is introduced by simulating a moving user traffic scenario for the eMBB slice at 110 ms . Our proposed drift handling framework promptly detected change in user traffic during the time interval of $[110 - 150]\text{ ms}$ and identified its nature as sudden drift, leading to an immediate retraining action. The retrained model was successfully replaced at 230 ms . In comparison, other frameworks such as CNDH and OCDD detected the user traffic changes at different times 150 ms and 260 ms and replaced the retrained model at 270 ms and 380 ms , respectively.

Figure 16 represents a sampled PMF. Here, the OCDD framework exhibits a maximum of 15% occurrences at 90 ms , 110 ms , and 130 ms , whereas the CNDH shows approximately 32% occurrences at 80 ms . In contrast, the proposed framework achieves approximately 48% occurrences at 50 ms . The proposed framework effectively determines the drift compared to the other frameworks.

Figure 16: Sampled PMF of drift detection for user traffic prediction use case

In summary, the proposed drift handling framework consistently outperforms other frameworks in various use cases, including QoS Prediction, CQI Prediction, and user traffic prediction. The choice of these three specific use cases is driven by their vital roles in B5G networks. QoS prediction ensures consistent network performance, while CQI prediction optimizes wireless communication, especially in varying channel conditions. User traffic prediction is essential for efficient resource allocation in dynamic B5G networks. These use cases demonstrate the adaptability and effectiveness of the proposed drift handling framework. Our proposed framework quickly detects drift events and employs effective adaptation strategies, setting it apart as a superior choice for managing changing network conditions.

6.6. Impact of Drift Adaptation on Control Loop Response Time

Drift adaptation, either by retraining or by selecting a suitable model based on the drift type, has an impact on the control loops due to different delays involved in AI/ML life cycle management as shown in Figure 17.

The total time required to deal with a drift scenario for RIC modules is $Total_{delay}$ is computed as:

$$Total_{delay} = T_p + T_{ico} + T_{co} + T_{mm} + T_{rt} + T_{rp} + T_{trs} \quad (5)$$

Whenever, AI/ML model management triggers retraining, T_{rp} is set to 0 and in case of triggering for replacement, T_{rt} is set to 0. The following is a brief description of each of the involved delays:

T_p : It is the required time to predict the desired RAN parameter for a given *LeadTime*. It plays a crucial role

Figure 17: Impact of different time delays in meeting the control loop response time at different time scales.

in meeting the control loop response time. Based on the experiments conducted in OpenStack platform with various VM-flavors, Table 4 shows that resources allocated to the AI/ML inference are inversely proportional to the prediction time. Another observation is that traditional time series models like TES, and DES exhibit negligible T_p whereas AI/ML time series models like LSTM and Transformer (TS) require a significant amount of resources.

Table 4: Prediction time and prediction accuracy

VM-Flavor	DES [ns]	TES [ns]	LSTM [ms]	TS [ms]
Small (1vCPU, 2GB RAM)	0.314	0.294	21.35	24.81
Medium (2vCPU, 4GB RAM)	0.292	0.221	15.31	19.13
Large (4vCPU, 8GB RAM)	0.211	0.111	6.12	8.31
XLarge (8vCPU, 16GB RAM)	0.08	0.08	0.3	0.3
Performance accuracy	DES	TES	LSTM	TS
RMSE	39	25	16	12

T_{ico} : The time delay involved between Near-RT and Non-RT RIC block communication. It varies depending on the deployment scenario. Most of the scenarios Near-RT RIC deployed at the edge and Non-RT RIC at the cloud which may take significant amount of time. Deploying both Near-RT and Non-RT RIC at the edge or cloud results in negligible amount of time to communicate between both of them. However, the deployment scenario varies based on the use case.

T_{co} : The time spent at the AI/ML continuous operation module for providing feedback to the AI/ML model management module. This includes the time taken for monitoring, verification, analysis, and continuous optimization of KPIs and also time required for policy enforcement. Resources available in the Non-RT RIC have a significant impact on T_{co} .

T_{mm} : Our proposed drift handling framework runs inside the AI/ML model management module. It is responsible for drift detection, analysis, and adaptation. The time

required for drift detection and adaptation can take a significant amount of time. Resources allocated in Non-RT RIC are also important.

T_{rt} : Whenever the AI/ML model management triggers retraining of the current model, then the time required for the retraining is T_{rt} . Resources at the Non-RT RIC site have a significant impact on T_{rt} . Training the traditional time series models like TES and DES would be easier due to their simple architecture to learn whereas AI/ML time series models like LSTM and Transformer take longer time due to their complex architecture to learn weights.

T_{rp} : If AI/ML model management triggers replacement for the current model with a best suitable model, the time required to identify the best suitable model from the available models in Non-RT RIC is T_{rp} . Our proposed *Dynamic ML Model Selection for Replacement* (i.e. Algorithm 4) chooses a model from the set of models which are periodically retrained in Non-RT RIC. A set of ML models selected by our Algorithm 4 are updated with the newly arrived distribution so that it can recover from drift scenario and perform prediction further. Resources in the Non-RT has an impact on T_{rp} .

T_{trs} : AI/ML model management triggers whether to retrain the model or replace it with another best suitable model to adapt to the drift. Once the model is ready, the time required to transfer its inference to Near-RT RIC using O1 interface is T_{trs} . The deployment scenario significantly impacts T_{trs} . If both Near-RT and Non-RT RIC are deployed at one site (i.e. edge or cloud) then T_{trs} is negligible.

In order to meet the control loop response, we need to select the best deployment scenario as well as resources so that all the aforementioned time delays can be optimal.

7. Conclusions and Future Directions

This paper presented a drift handling framework for Open RAN to maintain SLAs and maximize resource utilization. To address the drift, the proposed framework first detected the drift and then analyzed it to select an adequate drift adaptation strategy. The proposed drift handling framework is evaluated by implementing on the

OSC and OAI FlexRIC platforms for three different use cases. The performance results show that the proposed drift detection algorithm outperforms the state-of-the-art algorithm by detecting drift promptly after its occurrence, reducing SLA violations significantly. Furthermore, this paper investigated the impact of different timing delays in AI/ML life cycle management on control loop response time during drift adaptation.

In this paper, the models are trained on our custom built Non-RT RIC and deployed into the Near-RT RIC through *dms_cli* tool. However, in real-time scenario model training might take a significant amount of time, which could impact control loops response time of Open RAN depending on the resources. Future work will focus on investigating the impact of model training on various critical operations of the Open RAN, and predicting when and where (edge or cloud) to retrain the model.

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